

CONTROL PARAMETERS IN THE MANUFACTURE OF PREPREGS

by
Roderick Banks¹, Floreana Coman², Sabu John¹, Roxy Rosu³ & Wayne Cook⁴

1. RMIT University, School of Aerospace, Mechanical & Manufacturing Engineering, Bundoora East Campus, Vic. 3083, Australia.
2. Technical & Business Manager, Australian Composites Pty. Ltd, 124-132 Cochranes rd, Moorabbin, Vic 3189, Australia.
3. Research scientist, CRC-Advanced Composite structures, 506 Lorimer Street, Fishermans bend VIC 3207, Australia.
4. Department of Physics and Materials Engineering, Monash University Vic 3800, Australia.

SUMMARY: This study discusses on-going work using low-temperature curing prepregs for novel applications. This paper discusses various parameters involved in the control of optimal prepreg-properties processes for various product applications. A major component of this study involved the measurement of tack and its relationship to level of cure and its effect on drapability. Various methods to quantify drape are reported and assessed. These include the Bias-extension, Picture-frame, sphere drape and bending stiffness tests. Also, regarding the tack test as described in ASTM D 3167, several parameters not specified in the standard such as crosshead/peel rate, relative to preform testing direction and temperature, humidity and pressure, were examined. Optimal levels of cure for various resin-fibre systems are reported.

KEY WORDS: Prepreg, Tack, Bias-extension test, Rheology, Level of Cure (LoC)

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important factors governing the use of prepregs is their handling and draping characteristics. The draping ability of a prepreg can be simply defined as its ability to conform to the surface of tool surface without wrinkling. The other important handling and draping characteristic is known as tack, which is the ability a prepreg has in adhering to prepreg stack or tool surface. When manufacturing prepregs the parameters influencing the draping and handling characteristics include resin rheology, preform architecture and resin-to-reinforcement volume ratio. The selection of preform architecture is usually determined by the structural requirements of the application. Resin rheology is usually dependent on two variables, temperature and level of cure. Hand laid prepregs (which are the focus of this paper) tend to be laid at room temperatures, so when investigating the draping and handling characteristics, resin degree of cure is a major control variable in the manufacturing process. This paper examines the draping and handling of prepregs as function of cure.

For a woven fabric to conform to the surface of a tool with a compound curvature it undergoes several types of deformation, those being: intra-ply shear; yarn extension; relative yarn slip; out-of-plane bending and inter-ply slippage shown in Figure 1 (Long 2000). Out of these deformation modes, it has been generally accepted that the most significant deformation modes during forming operations are out-of-plane bending, inter-ply slippage and intra-ply shear (Nguyen 2002). Hand laid prepregs are generally laid down ply by ply, so when considering the handling and draping characteristics of a prepreg this research is concerned only with intra-ply shear, out-of-plane bending and tack.

Figure 1 Deformation modes (Arimitsu and Chou 1999; Long 2000)

The experimental investigation this paper describes was conducted by making up 5 prepregs using vacuum transfer resin infusion (VTRI), each prepreg accompanied with a sample of neat resin, each prepreg and resin sample set staged to differing levels of cure from each other. The prepregs were tested for intra-ply stiffness and bending stiffness and the rheology of the resin samples was defined.

MANUFACTURE OF THE TEST PREPREGS

The Vacuum Transfer Resin Infusion setup is shown in Figure 2. In order to minimize the amount of variables such that the resin rheology was dependent on just temperature and level of cure, a solvent free epoxy resin system was chosen, a 0.9 stoichiometric mix of D.E.R. 331 and Ethacure 100 Curative. A 385 gsm tight glass plain weave preform was chosen to make the prepregs from. This fabric exhibited good robustness, which was important for the intra-ply shearing tests to minimize any pre-shear. The glass volume fraction of the wet prepreg was $49\pm 3\%$.

Figure 2 Vacuum Transfer Resin Infusion (VTRI)

Preliminary curing tests on the prepregs were done at elevated temperatures inside an oven over short periods of time. The cure throughout each prepreg was inconsistent, probably due to the temperature

variation within the oven. The resin system was found to cure very slowly at room temperature, so the prepregs were left out on a bench at room temperature over a period of about two weeks to stage them. A 2mm deep dish filled with resin was left at the side of the curing prepregs – the assumption being the resin in the dish given the same time temperature history as the prepregs and with a similar geometry would be at the same level of cure. This way level of cure and rheology analysis could be conducted effectively on the resin inside the prepregs without needing to remove the resin from the prepregs which was found to be almost impossible. At the time intervals shown in Table 1 each prepreg ply accompanied by a 50ml sample of resin (taken from the 2mm deep dish) were put in a freezer at -18°C so that the level of cure was held until testing. A release film needed to be put on the prepreg ply before they were lifted to prevent the prepreg plies from in-plane distortion. This was very important for the in-plane shear stiffness tests.

Table 1 Prepreg Exposure times @ R.T and Level of Cure

Prepreg number	Time out at Room Temperature	Level of Cure
1	5hrs	0.012836
2	53hrs	0.191964
3	77hrs	0.257501
4	101hrs	0.292191
5	173hrs	0.566322

LEVEL OF CURE (LoC) OF THE PREPREGS

Mid-infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy was used to measure the level of cure of the prepregs. The machine used was a Perkin Elmer FT-IR Spectrometer 1725 X. The peak at 915 cm⁻¹ was used to measure the disappearance of the epoxy group (Jovan 1996). Various reference peaks were examined and the most reproducible results were obtained using the Benzene ring absorption at 1590 cm⁻¹. The LoC values are shown in Table 1.

RHEOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) was done on neat resin specimens using a RSIII Parallel Plate rheometer to gain an understanding of the viscous-elastic behaviour of the resin system. The relationships between the viscous-elastic parameters are shown below. For further information regarding viscous-elasticity refer to (Winter and Mours 1997). 25mm plates were used for the first four resin samples while 8mm plates were used for the fifth sample. The samples were tested at 25 °C with a strain of 1% over frequencies (ω) varying from 1 to 20 rad/sec.

$$E^* = \sqrt{(E')^2 + (E'')^2} = \text{complex vis cos ity} \quad (1)$$

where :

G' = gain shear modulus

G'' = loss shear modulus

$\tan \delta = G''/G' = \text{loss tangent}$

$$E' = \frac{G''}{\omega} = \text{real part of complex vis cos ity}$$

$$E'' = \frac{G'}{\omega} = \text{imaginary part of complex vis cos ity}$$

$$E^* = \sqrt{(E')^2 + (E'')^2} = \text{complex vis cos ity}$$

From resin sample 1 to resin sample 5 the complex viscosity increases by five orders of magnitude as shown in Figure 3. The loss tangent is indicative of the viscous-elastic behavior of the resin system - the lower $\tan \delta$ is the greater the elasticity. The resin system becomes more elastic as the LoC increases as shown by Figure 6. Isothermal plots of $\tan \delta$ have been used by researchers (Eloundou, Feve et al. 1996; Winter and Mours 1997; Dean, Cook et al. 2001) to identify the gelation points of thermosetting resin systems, according to the criteria outlined in Table 2. At low levels of cure the loss tangent is jumbled which was probably due to the phase shift being too low such that that experimental noise overshadowed it. At cure levels between 0.25 and 0.56 the lower frequencies were giving higher loss tangent values than the higher frequencies indicating that the resin system had not gelled, however the loss tangent is around three meaning that the elastic response is making a very significant contribution to the overall modulus. For vitrification no rigid criterion has been defined, however the conditions outlined in Table 3 are indicative that the resin system has vitrified (Lange, Altmann et al. 2000). G' (Figure 5) showed frequency dependence from the very outset, when the resin system was clearly not vitrified, otherwise none of the vitrification conditions were met. Figure 4 shows the effect of loss shear modulus (G'') with level of cure. This showed a steady increase of G'' and no peak thus indicating vitrification was absent. It is unlikely the resin system vitrified at any point. The resin system neither gelled nor vitrified for the 5 prepregs made.

Table 2 Gelation Criterion

	G'	G''	$\tan \delta$
just before gelation	$\propto \omega^2$	$\propto \omega$	higher $\omega >$ lower ω
at gelation	$\propto \omega$	$\propto \omega$	Frequency independent
just after gelation	frequency independent	$\propto \omega$	lower $\omega >$ higher ω

Table 3 Indications of Vitrification

Criterion	Definition
Vitrification 1	Onset of frequency dependence in G'
Vitrification 2	Peak in $\tan \delta$
Vitrification 3	Peak in G''
Vitrification 4	End of Frequency dependence in G'

Figure 3 Eta* of prepreg resin system versus LoC 1% strain

Figure 4 G'' of prepreg resin system versus LoC at 1% strain

Figure 5 G' of prepreg resin system versus LoC at 1% strain

Figure 6 $\text{Tan } \delta$ of prepreg resin system versus LoC at 1% strain

IN-PLANE SHEAR STIFFNESS OF THE PREPREGS

The two most commonly used shear stiffness tests are the picture-frame and the bias-extension tests shown in Figure 7. The advantage with the bias-extension test is that it is fast to prepare a sample, whereas great care must be taken when loading up the picture-frame with a sample as misaligned tows will result in large tensions developing within the sample resulting in erroneous results (Nguyen 2002). The advantage with the picture-frame test is the shear angle can be calculated directly from the crosshead displacement, whereas the shear angle must be measured with the bias-extension test as the specimen is subject to inter-tow slippage (Potter 2002) such that the shearing angle can not be calculated directly from the crosshead displacement. The tensile testing machine used was an Instron 1185 with a 1KN load cell. The picture-frame test was initially trialed, however the VTRI manufactured prepregs had slight misalignment due to prior handling, which lead to erratic results.

The bias-extension test was adopted as the shear stiffness test for these experiments. A sample size of 160x400mm was used, which is larger than the typical 80x200 mm sample size adopted by other researches (Wang 1997). This increased size was chosen to reduce tow slippage.

Figure 7 Picture-frame test & Bias-extension Test

It was likely the slippage between the five different prepregs would vary given the viscosity of the neat resin varied by five orders of magnitude, so when comparing the shear stiffness of the different prepregs, it was important to plot against shear angle rather than crosshead displacement. Measuring the shearing angle by taking photos periodically and using image analysis software was acceptably accurate provided the camera was properly setup such that the location on the sample surface where the angle was being measured was inline and perpendicular to the focal axis of the camera. These particular prepregs buckled for shearing angles beyond 20° such that this was not the case. Measuring the angle directly, by stopping the test was seen as the only accurate way of measuring the shearing angle. With dry fabric, stopping and restarting the test did not appear to effect the slippage, or the shape of the force crosshead displacement curve other than a sharp drop off then a sharp pick up in force local to where the test was stopped. However as can be seen in Figure 2 the higher the cure of the resin matrix the slower the load was to recover once the test was started again. Prepreg 5 had the greatest shearing stiffness, which would be expected as it had the highest viscosity.

Figure 8 Bias-extension test, force versus crosshead displacement

Figure 9 Bias-extension test, force versus shearing angle

Figure 9 plots shearing angle versus measured force, which tells a slightly different story on the effect of resin viscosity as shown in Figure 8. In Figure 8 the dry fabric appears to have greater shearing stiffness than prepregs 1 and 2. However in doing this comparison the assumption is made that the shearing angle is only dependant on the crosshead displacement. The influences of resin viscosity are most apparent in the earlier stages of shearing. As the shearing angle increase the curves, with the exception of specimen 5 seem to converge. This indicates that the influence of resin viscosity on the shearing stiffness diminishes as the shearing angle increases.

TACK TESTING

The choice of tack test was made easily as the industrial partner in the project had already adopted an adaptation of ASTM D 3167 ‘Standard Test Method for Floating Roller Peel Resistance of Adhesives’(Figure 10) for their quality assurance tack testing. The Samples were prepared by applying a pressure of 10 Kpa for 1 minute to adhere the prepreg strips to the rigid adherand. The crosshead rate was

100mm/minute. Prepregs 1 and 2 were messy to handle as some the resin would come off onto the hand. Prepregs 2 and 3 was were tacky to handle, prepreg 4 had a small amount of handling tack while prepreg 5 felt completely tack-less.

Sample 4 had the highest Tack peel force as shown by Figure 11. Samples 1, and 2 both left resin behind on the adherand, failing cohesively within the resin. Samples 3 and 4 left almost no trace behind whilst sample 5 left no trace of resin on the adherand. Prepregs 3, 4 and 5 demonstrated a more adhesive failure, failing at the interface between the resin and the adherand. At lower levels of cure, the resin flows more freely and completely wets the adherand, but the resin itself is not very strong and fails easily. The prepregs at the higher levels of cure do not wet the adherand as completely but are much stronger, failure is between the interface of the resin and the adherand. For a given resin system, preform type, glass volume fraction and contact conditions there is a level of cure where the wetting ability and cohesive strength ratio are an optimum for producing a prepreg with maximum tack.

Figure 10 Tack peel test

Figure 11 Prepreg tack versus LoC.

BENDING STIFFNESS OF PREPREGS

Figure 12 Cantilever Test

The bending stiffness of the prepregs was measured using ASTM D1388-96, known as the self-weight Cantilever Test shown in Figure 12. The Fabric strip is positioned so that part of its length projects from the edge of a horizontal surface. The fabric strip is slowly slid over the edge until the tip of the strip makes contact with a surface, which is inclined at an angle of 41.5° from the edge of the horizontal surface. The overhang length at this point is taken and then used to calculate the bending stiffness using the following formulae in Equation 2.

$$G = W \times c^3 \quad (2)$$

where

c = bending length (cm), o = length of overhang (cm), W = areal weight $mg\ cm^{-2}$, G = flexural rigidity ($mg\ cm$)
 $c = o/2$

Prepreg Specimens were cut into dimensions of $250mm \times 30mm$. The samples were cut in the bias direction, as in this direction the viscosity of the resin would have the greatest influence in the overall stiffness of the prepreg. This test is intended for elastic materials however the prepregs exhibited viscous-elastic properties such that the strip would creep – rather than droop instantaneously and then hold its position, as would an elastic strip. To overcome this it was decided to increment the overhang, if the strip failed to touch the ramp within 30 seconds. The prepreg strip was re-straightened after each droop. Not surprisingly the stiffness increased as the level of cure was increased as shown in Figure 12 below.

Figure 12 Out-of-Plane Bending Stiffness versus Level of Cure.

CONCLUSION

Given that the sample size for the bias-extension test would be comparable to the area an operator might be shearing while laying a prepreg, prepreg number 5 would be unworkable as a force of over 500N was required to produce any appreciable shear which would far exceed the strength of most humans. Beyond that the desirable level of cure is not really clear-cut. Prepregs 1 and 2 were messy to handle, had low tack, but had the lowest shear stiffness at low angles of shear. Prepreg 4 would probably be the most suitable prepreg for the majority of applications. It had the highest peel tack, was good to handle, its shearing and bending stiffness were not appreciably higher than prepregs 1, 2 or 3. From these experiments for hand laid prepregs being used at room temperature it would appear that the optimum resin complex viscosity (Eta^*) would be in the order of magnitude of 10^4 Pascal seconds.

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